

Adducts of Palladium(II)-bis-(2-Guanidiniumbenzimidazole) Salts with Pyridine and Ammonia

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Tetra coordinated palladium(II) bis (2 Guanidiniumbenzimidazole) complexes when treated with ammonia or pyridine, show further coordination of two molecules of ammonia or pyridine. These adducts are diamagnetic and possibly are tetragonal in structure.

THE number of known compounds in which the coordination number of bi-valent palladium exceeds four is relatively few. However, it is possible to obtain quinque- or sexi-coordinated complexes of palladium(II) in solution¹, when a sufficiently high concentration of halide ions are present, e.g., $[\text{PdCl}_6]^{4-}$ and $[\text{PdBr}_6]^{4-}$. The tertiary arsine $\text{MeAs}[(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{AsMe}_2]_2$ gives sexi-covalent complex $[\text{Pd}(\text{II})(\text{Trs})_2]^{2+}$. The single crystal X-ray studies² indicate that in the solid state the di-iodide contains a sexi-covalent complex of palladium(II), with iodide ions in the trans position. The apparently quinqi-covalent complex of the type $[\text{Pd}(\text{Diarsine})_2\text{Hal}]^{2+}$ (Hal = Cl, Br or I), could also be sexi-covalent in solution, if the presence of a solvent molecule in the sixth position is postulated. Fackler *et. al.*³ prepared 1 : 1 adducts between methyl-diphenylphosphine and Pt(II) and Pd(II) and have characterised them to be five-coordinate complexes. It has also been reported⁴ that the interaction of tertiary phosphines with bis-(diphenyl-phosphine dithionate) palladium(II) give 1 : 1 and sometimes 1 : 2 adducts, and by physical measurements concluded that they are genuine five- and six-coordinated complexes.

The four-coordinated palladium(II)-bis-(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole) complexes⁵ when treated with ammonia gas or pyridine formed adducts with two molecules of ammonia or pyridine.

Experimental

Palladium (II)-bis-(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole), salts, both red and cream variety, dissolved in pyridine, forming pale greenish yellow solutions. The palladium complexes were kept in pyridine solution for 48 hrs. and then the pyridine was allowed to evaporate at the ordinary temperature (20°). *Dirty greenish yellow* powder, adhered with a little pyridine was left as residue. On triturating the residue in a glass mortar at a temperature of 10°, the adhered pyridine gradually escaped and the products were quickly transferred to glass stoppered sample tubes

These pyridine adducts were not very stable and lose pyridine slowly when exposed to the atmosphere. The loss of pyridine was very slow at lower temperatures (below 10°), and the rate of loss increased with the rise in temperature, as well as in presence of moisture. After 48 hrs, loss of pyridine was complete and the dirty greenish yellow powder changed over to the cream coloured α -palladium complex salts.

There was change in the colour of the α - and β -palladium(II)-bis-(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole) salts, when kept in a desiccator charged with KOH and ammonia gas for 3-4 days. The chloride formed *pale yellow* powder, the sulphate, *dirty-yellow* powder and the nitrate *dirty-brown* powder. These adducts are quite stable at ordinary temperature. When kept exposed to the atmosphere, the ammonia-adducts very slowly lose ammonia molecules. But when the moist adducts were slowly warmed over a water-bath, those gave out readily the ammonia molecules and changed over to the parent cream-coloured complex. Table 1 shows the analyses of the pyridine and ammonia adducts.

The pyridine and ammonia adducts were diamagnetic like the parent complexes. Electronic absorption spectra of the palladium(II)-bis-(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole) complexes in pyridine were taken in a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with one cm cell. The results are shown in Table 2.

Infra red spectra in nujol mull were taken in Perkin Elmer 521 spectrophotometer for palladium (II)-bis-(2-Guanidiniumbenzimidazole) chloride and nitrate adducts. In both the cases a new band of medium intensity was observed at 815 cm^{-1} , which was absent in palladium-bis-(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole) chloride and nitrate.

Discussion

From analytical result it is found that these adducts are associated with two molecules of either pyridine and ammonia. In the case of ammonia adducts, NH_3 rocking vibration appeared as a new peak at

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TABLE 1

Compound	Found				Calculated			
	Pd	Anion	N	Py	Pd	Anion	N	Py
[X Py ₂]Cl ₂	15.6	10.1	24.3	22.6	15.5	10.4	24.5	23.0
[X Py ₂]SO ₄	15.2	13.7	23.5		15.0	13.5	23.6	
[X Py ₂](NO ₃) ₂	14.5		25.7	20.5	14.4		26.5	21.4
[X(NH ₃) ₂]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	18.5	12.1	28.9		18.4	12.3	29.1	
[X(NH ₃) ₂](SO ₄).H ₂ O	17.6	15.9	26.8		17.6	15.9	27.4	
[X(NH ₃) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ .H ₂ O	16.6		28.9		16.8		30.1	

815 cm⁻¹. The presence of this band proves that the ammonia molecules are coordinated to the metal.

TABLE 2

Compound	Absorptions
[X]Cl ₂	12820 cm ⁻¹ and 17230 cm ⁻¹
[X]SO ₄	13160 cm ⁻¹ and 16950 cm ⁻¹
[X](NO ₃) ₂	12740 cm ⁻¹ and 16950 cm ⁻¹

Tetra-coordinated palladium (II) complexes are generally square-planar, and palladium(II)-bis-(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole) complexes have been found to form square-planar complexes, which are either pink or red in colour⁵. In these adducts the two ligands, 2-guanidinobenzimidazole, coordinated to the palladium metal through the nitrogen atom lie in one plane, forming four-coordinated square-

planar complex, with two ammonia or pyridine molecules in the axial position, but farther apart than the other nitrogen atoms, thereby forming highly tetragonal structure similar to the corresponding nickel (II)⁶ and copper(II)⁷ octahedral adducts. The ammonia adducts are stabler than the pyridine adducts, suggesting that the metal to ligand bond is stronger in the former than the latter one.

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